

Annex 5 - Replication Sheet

Institutional Landscape Analysis (Pillar I)

Case study: IN-HABIT – Córdoba

What

Institutions shaping how GDEI is:

- regulated
- resourced
- implemented
- monitored

Why

GDEI fails when:

- mandates stay symbolic
- no resources follow
- accountability is weak

How

8w Institutional survey [Go to Annex 1](#)

0.5w Index construction [Go to Annex 2](#)

0.5w Radar visualisation [Go to Annex 2](#)

1w SWOT reflection

Total duration: **10 weeks**

Six diagnostic dimensions

- Stakeholder involvement
- Political commitment
- Legal framework
- Resources & structures
- Accountability
- Data & knowledge

Institutional profile – Córdoba

Scores normalised on a 0–5 scale

Córdoba – SWOT-style interpretation

Strengths

- Strong legal mandate for GDEI
- Clear quantified equality targets
- Dedicated councillor for equality and gender
- Equality strategy covering 10 policy areas

Weaknesses

- No evaluation of GDEI impacts
- Very limited use of independent research
- Weak stakeholder involvement
- No dedicated GDEI budget or department
- Monitoring limited to gender budgeting

Key insight:

Political and legal commitment is strong, but implementation capacity, evidence use and monitoring remain fragile.

Replication takeaway

Combine surveys, indices, visuals and stakeholder mapping to expose where institutional ambition stops short of delivery.

Next steps: choosing the right tool

Do you have a clear baseline assessment of your institutional capacity for GDEI? (mandate, structures, resources, accountability, data)

Do you have sufficient resources and data to implement and monitor change? (budget, staff time, data standards, access to datasets)

Do you need a time-bound plan to address identified gaps? (owners, deliverables, deadlines, monitoring)

Are you designing or revising a concrete policy or programme?

Participatory gender audit

See GDEI Handbook p.35

Gender mainstreaming architecture, Stakeholder mapping

See GDEI Handbook p.37

GDEI action plan

See GDEI Handbook p.40

Pillar II – Policies

See GDEI Handbook p.10

Annexes

Annex 1 - Institutional Landscape Questionnaire

1. Political and Executive

• Members of city government by gender	/ Total members	
• Members of political parties by gender	Women / Total members	
• Is there a member of the government with specific role on equal opportunities?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
• Is there a member of the government with specific role on gender equality?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
• Are there stated political objectives on equal opportunities/gender equality?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
• Does the city government state targets and measures in terms of equal opportunities/gender equality?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No

2. Administration

a) Is promoting gender equality/equal opportunities part of the organisation general mandate?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
b) Is gender/equal opportunities mainstreaming integrated in the regulations of the city administration?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
c) Is there an administrative department on equal opportunities?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
I. If yes, how many staff it employs?		
		Answer 2d

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II.	If yes, what is the last annual budget allocated to that department?	Answer 2d / Answer 2d	
III.	If yes, what was the annual budget allocated to that department		
	one year before?	Answer 2d / Answer 2d <input type="checkbox"/>	
	No budget that year		
	two years before?	Answer 2d / Answer 2d <input type="checkbox"/>	
	No budget that year		
	three years before?	Answer 2d / Answer 2d <input type="checkbox"/>	
	No budget that year		
d)	Has the city administration an Equality Strategy in place?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
I.	If yes, what period does it cover?	Answer 2e	
II.	If yes, what areas does it cover:		
	i. Finance?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	ii. Social services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	iii. Transport?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	iv. Sport and Leisure?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	v. Culture?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	vi. Health?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	vii. Education?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	viii. Economic activities?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	ix. Environment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	x. Housing?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	xi. Urban and planning?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	xii. Work/Labour market?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	xiii. Other?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Answer 2e	
e)	Has the city administration, in the last five years, carried out any of the following:		
I.	Equality audit	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
		When last Answer 2f_I	When next Answer 2f_I

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II.	Equality impact assessment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2f_II	Answer 2f_II		
III.	Equality evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2f_III	Answer 2f_III		
IV.	Equality stakeholder consultations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2f_IV	Answer 2f_IV		
V.	Gender budgeting?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2f_V	Answer 2f_V		
f) Does the administration run surveys of the population in the following areas (whether separately or in combination)?							
		Yes	No	When last	When next	By gender	Any other group
I.	Finance?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_I	Answer 2g_I	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
II.	Social services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_II	Answer 2g_II	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
III.	Transport?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_III	Answer 2g_III	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
IV.	Sport and Leisure?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_IV	Answer 2g_IV	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V.	Culture?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_V	Answer 2g_V	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
VI.	Health?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_VI	Answer 2g_VI	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
VII.	Education?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_VII	Answer 2g_VII	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
VIII.	Economic activities?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_VIII	Answer 2g_VIII	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
IX.	Environment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_IX	Answer 2g_IX	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
X.	Housing?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_X	Answer 2g_X	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
XI.	Urban and planning?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_XI	Answer 2g_XI	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
XII.	Work/Labour market?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_XII	Answer 2g_XII	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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XIII.	Other?	Please specify <input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_XIII	Answer 2g_XIII	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
g) Has the administration collected any gender disaggregated data in any of the following area in the last five years?						
I.	Population and demography?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
II.	Transport?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
III.	Health?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
IV.	Education?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
V.	Culture?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
VI.	Sport?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
VII.	Environment?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
VIII.	Housing?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
IX.	Economic activities?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
X.	Urban and Planning?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
XI.	Work/Labour market?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
XII.	Other?		Please specify		<input type="checkbox"/>	No

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Annex 2 - How to represent the Institutional Landscape

The Questionnaire in Annex 1 collects a range of information and data for the six dimensions of the Pillar. Most of the questions ask for the presence (or absence) of specific GDEI tools and the specific areas covered. To analyse these data, we converted each answer into a numeric value. Therefore, each positive answer takes the value 1, while a negative answer is coded 0. When several items are grouped together by dimension, all dimensional values are summed up together and this sum is divided by the total number of items in the respective dimension. This ensures that the final dimensional value is between 0 and 1. We can interpret this score as either the average number of positive answers per item in the dimension or the share of positive answers in the dimension. Only three questions result in numeric values: these are the gender compositions of governing assemblies, the gender composition of local workforces; the annual budget of GDEI departments. We need to convert these values into a 0-1 range as per other variables/dimensions above. Gender compositions are defined as the share of women in a position, so we can transform such share into an inequality measure that is bounded between 0 and 1, with 1 indicating no inequality. More formally, we compute the absolute difference between the share of women in a position and the ideal equal distribution (i.e. 50%) divided by 50. This can be interpreted as the relative change in women's share necessary to achieve an equal distribution. Then, we subtract this value from 1 so that it is monotonically increasing and has its maximum at 1. Note that, with such formulation, an excess of women is treated similarly as an excess of men. We have now transformed all scores into variables between 0 and 1. We sum all of them by dimension, and because not all dimensions have the same number of items, we rescale all dimension indices so that they have the same maximum. Formally, the rescaling factors are computed for each dimension as the maximum theoretical value in all dimensions

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divided by the maximum theoretical value in the rescaled dimension. These computed indices can then be plotted into radar diagrams as the one shown in Figure 1.

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